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Cross-Disciplinary Creative Engineering Education with Internet of Things Technologies

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ABSTRACT

Due to the developments of sensor networks, RFID and information processing technologies, remarkable breakthroughs have been made for the Internet of Things (IoT) applications. In order to successfully implement the IoT applications, effective solutions linked to the cross-cutting issues will be an important subject in future engineering education. Therefore, instead of applying a traditional single-discipline lecturing approach, this project aims to conduct project-oriented learning and use the application development training as a concrete embodiment of the interdisciplinary engineering education, which makes the transition from being a student to establishing a creative design. For achieving cultivation of creative thinking and the realization of interdisciplinary engineering education, two representative trainings are conducted: (A) Proposing human-centric application proposals with Internet of Things techniques and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems. Essentially there are four major steps involved in this one-year project: (1) Integrating creative and design thinking with social care infrastructures and local services (e.g., visiting a nursing home, a special education school for the deaf, or a fire station), (2) Developing applications of Internet of Things (proposing a specific problem statement), (3) Embedded system implementations, and (4) Validating the system design via user feedback. On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which may allow the students to leverage IoT techniques and describe general issues of people-oriented problems through observation and discussion. This paper will present the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service.

Conference Key Areas: interdisciplinary engineering education,

Keywords: internet of things, interdisciplinary engineering education, creative thinking, embedded system implementations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the developments of sensor networks, RFID and information processing technologies, remarkable breakthroughs have been made for the Internet of Things (IoT) applications. In order to successfully implement the IoT applications, effective solutions linked to the cross-cutting issues will be an important subject in future engineering education. Therefore, instead of applying a traditional single-discipline lecturing approach, this project aims to conduct project-oriented learning and use the application development training as a concrete embodiment of the interdisciplinary engineering education, which makes the transition from being a student to establishing a creative design. For achieving cultivation of creative thinking and the realization of interdisciplinary engineering education, two representative trainings are conducted: (A) Proposing human-centric application proposals with Internet of Things techniques and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems.

At present, there are many creative competitions (for example: MediaTek Technology Networking Development Contest-2016 communication contest), but before the creative reality, how to cultivate the students to possess the concept of design thinking, so that students can use social care activities to translate their observations into insights into the products and applications that can improve human life, but a very important training experience. The notebook program will try to break through the traditional engineering education only focusing on single-domain phenomena, applications such as: Problem-based Learning, Project-based Learning teaching mode, and concludes other sub-plan themes, with the IoT platform and application as a specific cross-domain engineering education Implementation example. From the discovery of the problem, with the creative thinking of the notebook plan training and the design of the Internet, cultivate students with creative and complex problems to solve the logical thinking and technical knowledge, so that the general learners can be transformed into the training of creative people through the course of the realization.

Fig. 1. Emerging application domains: opportunities for IoT technologies [1]

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fire station), (2) Developing applications of Internet of Things (proposing a specific problem statement), (3) Embedded system implementations, and (4) Validating the system design via user feedback. On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which may allow the students to leverage IoT techniques and describe general issues of people-oriented problems through observation and discussion. This paper will present the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design processes and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service.

2. Human-Centric Design Process

This project explores the learning experience by integrating creative and design thinking with social care infrastructures and local services. Using the process of design thinking presented by Stanford (Fig. 2 (left)), learners can translate their observations into insights, products and applications that can improve human life. Note that although the thinking process is human-centred, it is a system design viewpoint. Furthermore, the industrial mentor may be consulted to guide the learners from discovering problems, defining issues, proposing possible solutions, and finally finding the best solution by using the Double-Diamond Thinking mode (Fig. 2 (right)). It is to be hoped that through the idea of the concept of creativity training, students can gain experience and skills for proposing general issues, which may provide a basis for defining specific problems (Empathy and Define). Then, through the combination of creative thinking training and engineering education, an appropriate solution may be explored to solve the problem (Ideate, Prototype, and test).

Fig. 2. (a) Design thinking process [2] and (b) Double-diamond thinking model [3].

2.1 Phase I: Cross-Domain Perspectives

On the theme of creativity and design thinking workshops, several lectures and experience-sharing group discussions will be arranged. Related Topics cover: the technology and concept of creativity and design thinking, training procedures, tools, and the need and importance of creative thinking in engineering education. Hope that through this workshop activities and thoughts training, students can cultivate the ability to think creatively in engineering education. For instance, guide students to

think about the improvement of health-related quality of life and well-being by visiting the nursing house or the center for the mentally handicapped (Fig. 3), which leads the students to consider the design issue from cross-domain perspectives and may further provide a better solution for the caring of our society.

Fig. 3. The issues of caring for an aging society and handicapped people [4]

2.2 Phase II: Idea Proposal

Fig. 4. Key procedures in the design of application tasks [5]

As shown in Fig. 4, three types of tasks are considered in a design work: (1) manual task, (2) supported task, and (3) automatic task [5]. In a research and design process, the manual task includes the requirement analysis and application architecture design for the core application, such as listing the features required for application and supported properties. The analysis results provide the application designers to deconstruct the foundation of application architecture, dividing the main development concepts into several abstract design modules. Through the interaction of these abstract design modules and the exchange of service messages, the operation logic of the foundation and core application of network operation is established (Automatic Task). Afterwards, simulations of the application design and system implementation may be performed to verify the system behaviours, and then realize the optimum design of the core application (Supported Task). In order to render the conceptual design architecture diagram of the system, this project will illustrate the key technologies and hardware and software elements involved in the system design.

2.3 Phase III: Embedded system implementations

To conduct embedded system implementation, students usually need fundamental understanding on embedded system design. Since embedded system is by nature cross-discipline, from the perspective of lecturing a course, it can be a preliminary of advanced courses and focus on giving an overview of system design. For example, a traditional bachelor course on “embedded system” in EECS will introduce fundamentals of embedded hardware components and firmware. Labs are usually given to concrete the abstract concepts. On the other hand, it can also be an integration of core and fundamental courses (e.g., circuit design, VLSI, SOC) and can be further arranged as a senior course or a first year graduate course.

Nowadays, to accomplish a real world application with embedded systems, a variety of knowledge are required. For example, many applications require the ability to interact with outside world so that the network protocol stack should be included to access the Internet. For ease of implementation, many state-of-the-art embedded design platforms with OS ported are chosen, which implies that knowledge on system software, client-server programming, distributed and parallel architecture are thus required. Furthermore, to endow applications with intelligence, preliminary knowledge on data mining or machine learning may be needed. As can be seen that embedded system implementation involves many traditionally disjoint engineering disciplines, (e.g., OSs, MCs, programming languages, networks, applications, data analysis), a comprehensive education program on embedded system is essential to provide appropriate foundations for the embedded system design. Therefore, it is not

easy to convey comprehensive knowledge in one or two curricula so that students can complete their projects to a certain level.

A more efficient arrangement of a course on embedded system implementation is to adopt problem-based learning (PBL), which is a pedagogy where groups of students work together and apply practical techniques to solve a problem. The problem is an incentive that keeps students thinking and proposing a probable solution. It is also the motivation for students to learn the fundamental knowledge of embedded systems in order to complete their proposal. From the PBL aspects, we can detail only on embedded system components that are demanded to solve students' problems and convey other topics briefly. For example, to equip an application with automatic decision ability, classification techniques like regression or neural network may be lectured on, instead of a complete introduction to all data mining techniques. Besides, as the technology advances, more embedded hardware or software components are wrapped layeredly. For example, many circuits and chips of variety function are wrapped into SOC. This trend can be obviously seen as software components are also wrapped layer by layer into a high level module or API. Therefore, detailing the knowledge of all components for embedded system is even more difficult and may not be necessary for embed system implementation. However, applying PBL is not an easy task because defining a proper problem to arouse resonance and inspire discussion is difficult especially when students' preliminary knowledge is not sufficient or not consistently. A real problem given by cross-discipline experts is hard to solve expectedly while unrestrained imagination from students themselves are generally impractical.

Therefore, different from a traditional PBL course, we arrange a two-course program of IoT and embedded system to solve cross-discipline problems. In the first and 2nd stages, we stimulate the critical and creative thinking of students by 1) visiting real fields where IoT technology can be adequately applied, 2) lecturing IoT related knowledge, and 3) encouraging students to consider the design issue from cross-discipline perspectives and propose an IoT-based solution for the caring of our society. In the third stage, we encourage and guide students to apply embedded system technology to realize their ideas and proposals. To provide an incentive for the student to learn embedded systems, we continue the main theme of the IoT course and convey knowledge of embedded system under the framework of an IoT system. The course is arranged as a part of our master program for the students are more ready for PBL. We also encourage the senior students of our bachelor programs to go on the course strongly. In the course, students are grouped and collaborate to accomplish their project.

Specifically, with the goal of realizing students' proposal of an IoT application, we first give the fundamentals of embedded system. The main topics include an overview of embedded system, embedded system design flow, and major hardware

and software components. We are prone to guide the students to implement a prototype of their idea by applying the existing embedded system platform with OS as well as IoT sensors and IoT networks. Thus, although the embedded operation system plays as an important role of an embedded system, many components of OS, such as cache replacement mechanism, CPU scheduling, disk management, won't be detailed. Similarly, nor do we detail the theoretic perspective of how a microcontroller is designed, the MCU architecture, or the assembly language.

Fig. 5. An architecture of IoT Applications

Under the architecture of an IoT application as shown in Fig. 5, we will detail on I/O interface, interrupts and control mechanism, process operation w/wo OS, and data flow and storage. In addition to setting up a development environment, students will conduct the labs on building a basic IoT device to sensing data, integrating multiple sensors and performing a complex sensing task, interacting IoT device with IoT gateway, processing data among IoT device, IoT gateway, and the sever end. By the approach, we can avoid to integrate too much materials in a single course and can still promote student to complete their proposal to a certain degree.

2.4 Phase IV: Validating the system design

To validating the system design, we conduct opinion survey on both students as well as the users. Specifically, at the end of the second stage, the users as well as domain experts are invited to give suggestions on the ideas and the proposals based on student's demonstration. Students can grasp the chance to review their idea and proposals. In the third stage, students are encouraged to team up to participate in some contests like [6-7]. This is another chance for students to rethink the pros and cons. Finally, a creativity test on students will be conducted to evaluate the effect of the pedagogy on the student's creativity thinking at the fourth stage. The suggestion

of the users, the degree of accomplishment, the feedbacks from the student, and even the contest results are feedbacks to revise the content of the program.

3. Case Study

A course project may be applied to develop a practical application using IoT technologies. The students are grouped into teams to discuss application architectures from cross-disciplinary perspectives and propose their problem statements, project deliverables, system descriptions, project setups, prototype implementation, test and feedback. Accordingly, each team will deliver the full architecture of the system and the important pieces of implementation details. Here, we use an activity monitoring system as an example to describe the design issues. A team project example is depicted in Fig. 6, where students may design an IoT application from cross-disciplinary perspectives for rescue and environmental monitoring by visiting a working fire station.

Fig.6. Developing a practical application with creative thinking and IoT technologies.

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